

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KAMBA****FIRST NAME: RUVIMBO****PROGRAM CODE: MBASD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10 Pro)

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1)INTRODUCTION

Critical to any graduate students' skillset is the development of above par professional writing skills. Having been out of the formal tertiary education system for a decade now since completing my Bachelor's degree in a technical field, I found the knowledge shared critical to the setting up of a robust foundation towards not only attaining graduate certification but also towards personal career development. Tapping into the reading material provided in period 1, which includes a good mix of presentations and chapter extracts, definitely goes a long way towards advancing my knowledge and developing my writing skillset. Excellent writing skills are pertinent to business administration skills development because business management occurs within a very formal and professional environment; hence documentation of business ideas and proposals is key to business advancement/development. This paper seeks to outline the extent to which I interacted with and assimilated concepts mastered after studying the provided coursepack covering the basics of citation, writing styles, and grammar.

2)REFERENCING

Plagiarism is a serious academic offense that takes many forms. Chief amongst the forms of plagiarism that intrigued me was the fact that an aspiring, however not serious graduate student may consider someone writing a paper on their behalf and then personalizing by fixing their name on it before submitting it to their professor for assessment (EUCLID 2015, 10). Other plagiarism forms, as highlighted in the coursepack, include the commonly known plagiarism act of using someone else's information or quoting it word for word without acknowledging the source. To guard against this,

EUCLID advises that one cites all sources of any ideas, quotes, or other information acquired from a third source, however keeping in mind that it is inappropriate to cite common knowledge even if you are new to the topic. Reflecting upon it, I appreciated the validity of the point, and what it really means is that before authoring any document and citing anyhow, I must have widely researched on a topic of interest.

In-text citing entails using either in-text quotes bounded by quotation marks, long quotes for direct word for word quotes that are longer than four lines, or paraphrasing. Where appropriate, referencing of all materials cited in the paper is then done and presented as a list of works, otherwise known as a bibliography (EUCLID 2015, 33). EUCLID recommends installing an application called Zotero to ease the process of citing, in line with modern-day technological trends. I appreciate that the application is recommended in major paper development, but I find it practical to master its use from the onset, including when writing the response papers. I found this app remarkable in that one can create an easy-to-reference offline library of study materials in various formats from web-pages to ebooks and pdf files in Zotero. Referencing material from the Zotero library is then automated hence less taxing.

3) WRITING STYLES AND FORMATTING

I, for one, have learned through my work practice that the choice of which writing language to adopt depends on the audience. Upon reflecting on the lessons learnt having studied the coursepack, I realized that all this while I have been lumping both American and British English writing styles. I guess the confusion emanates from the fact that I am part of a project team implementing and therefore reporting on both British and American-funded development projects, but all I knew until I undertook this course is that the major difference is that of spellings and pronunciations so that is all I would focus on getting right. Little did I know there are a lot more parameters used to distinguish the two and that as one writes a paper, it is important to make an outright decision at the beginning of whether to adopt purely British or American English. EUCLIDuclid, through this course, has taught me that the difference between the two centers not only on spelling differences but factors in the relative placement of punctuation marks and that American English attracts wider usage amongst the English speakers and writers. All I knew since I learned how to write compositions from a primary school level was that periods, or full stops as they are popularly termed locally, should only be placed after the quotation marks. All these years I never imagined I could be violating the principles of writing in doing so since it employs parameters of both American and British English with the former being that of using quotation marks and not inverted commas while the latter is concerned with placing the period outside the quote as opposed to enclosing the period inside the quotation marks in the American style of writing (EUCLID 2015, 7). I realized, however, that it has mostly been the British English format I have been using, and I guess this inevitably is because Zimbabwe, which is where I schooled, was previously a British colony.

Speaking of rigid education systems, all I remember from my years of pursuing a Bachelor's Degree was that when citing, one should use the Harvard style. I do not recall the reason why it was chosen, but all I remember is I was taught how to master just that

and, therefore, never knew anything about other writing styles in existence. Thanks to the course reading material provided by EUCLID, I now know there is a pool of writing styles from which to select and that the choice of the Rule of Style to adopt varies between disciplines and also depends on the target audience. I now know that Style is much more than just citing as it encompasses aspects to do with the correct use of punctuations, grammar, and vocabulary, length of the sentence, font usage among a lot more aspects (EUCLID 2015, 52). EUCLID recommends students use the Chicago Rules (Turabian) Style of writing, and this paper is my first ever written in that format, but I must admit that when it comes to referencing, Turabian and Harvard seem more or less the same to me. Paragraph styles are different, on the other hand, as they are concerned with just formatting, and these are then automatically referenced in the table of contents.

4) WRITING STRUCTURE AND BASICS OF WRITING

All knowledge gained through studying the course pack is useful and best applied by abiding by the basics of writing outlined at the beginning in what EUCLID terms the basics of essay writing. Fundamental as it might seem, it is important to remember throughout the writing process that a well thought out and orderly presented written paper is essential in attracting the readers' attention. Writing to convince is never a transparent cut linear process and involves several stages beginning with the stage of critical planning in good time (EUCLID 2015, 2). One would need to develop a well-informed guide to their writing that answers critical questions in an obviously orderly manner that is informed by thorough research. Achieving this, therefore, calls for not only extensive reading coupled with note-taking for research purposes but, more importantly, thinking critically and creatively throughout all the stages of writing. This enables a draft work to be put in place, which obviously follows the principles of introduction first, body, and lastly, the conclusion. EUCLID suggests that the introduction and conclusion be written after the body has been completed leaving one in a more informed position of what exactly their writing focus is on (EUCLID 2015, 4). I find EUCLID's suggestion really useful, especially considering that all along I have been writing following the order of my work's presentation starting off with the introduction. I grasped much later in life the concept of the use of computers in writing, which admittedly presents a comparatively better advantage of allowing easy and smart reorganizing of sentences and paragraphs versus the traditional pen and paper writing which I first mastered.

5) CONCLUSION

In addition to perfecting my academic writing skills, this period's study package will contribute immensely towards my personal and professional writing skills. Ethically it was regarded as inappropriate to write in the first person, but I realize it is so natural that it allows me to have an immediate connection with what I am writing so much that I believe concepts are easier to remember if told my way. Admittedly, I have never blogged to date due to lack of that art of writing freely using my own words, despite having a lot of information to share. Putting together this response paper has unlocked the secret keys to

my ability to write more papers. I believe this period has enriched my personal, academic, and professional writing skills all at once. I now know that writing skills are not just about what I think is correct but is all about taking time to understand the intended audience and making an effort to flex the way I prepare and present the paper. Sustainable Development is topical, and jumping on the discussions, and unlocking opportunities depends on the ability to entice people who are passionate about it. As such, enrolling for my Masters in Business Administration in Sustainable Development with EUCLID was the best decision I have made for myself. The foundation of writing skills is, therefore, very practical and handy.

REFERENCES

Euclid University. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*.

<https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401-period-1/> (accessed on 20 January 2020).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.